

Kinship as a Key to Keeping Traditions

Dr. C. Justin Selvaraj

*Assistant Professor and Head
Department of Fine Arts and Aesthetics
School of Performing Arts
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai*

Abstract

It aims to dedicate to family, kinship from folklore founding various genres particularly on oral narratives. Oral narratives, particularly proverbs, have been taken into consideration for analysing the social aesthetics of oral tradition. In general, proverbs ordinarily suggest a course of action or pass judgment on a situation. Roger D. Abrahams states that “proverbs are short and witty traditional expressions that arise as part of everyday discourse as well as in the more highly structured situations of education and judicial proceedings.” It is wise, belongs to a society, and is applied by an individual to a particular situation. From the proverbs it is observed that the reality of kinship relation by adopting different tools for analysing. Lineage is a term in kinship that gives meaning to a corporate descent group whose members can be traced by their genealogical links to a known common ancestor. In other words, it can also be taken as the kinship relationship between an individual and the individual’s ancestors. In terms of lineage, family system is identified through nuclear family, joint family as well. This paper is confined to dealing with the social aesthetics of oral tradition in which a parallel cousin (known as a “pangali” or “sharer”) bond is focused. As they are sharing their clan of each and every lineage, they are considered as pangali. Reflections from the folklore genre of proverb about the pangali are found in the following: each and every pangali is bound to be committed to everyone; as they share equal responsibility, it also has a reflexive nature in the ritual. Thus, it is an interesting phenomenon to study social aesthetics of oral tradition which focuses on kinship expression in proverbs of the obligatory ritual of an agnate (pangali) in family

Keywords: Kinship, Proverbs, Nadars, Folklore, Oral Tradition

Introduction

This article deals with proverbs that are still used among kin groups. In general, proverbs ordinarily suggest a course of action or pass judgment on a situation. Roger D. Abrahams states that “proverbs are short and witty traditional expressions that arise as part of everyday discourse as well as in the more highly structured situations of education and judicial proceedings.” (Abrahams) It is wise; it belongs to a society, and it is applied by an individual to a particular situation. (Taylor)

This article of Social Aesthetics of Oral Tradition mainly focuses on proverbs and exploring the meaning from a Tamil community. The term “social aesthetics” was first used in 1982 by the American Bill Olander. (Deitcher) It deals with ways of producing, interpreting, or presenting art and culture, so a concentration arises between aesthetic knowledge and the surrounding society. As social aesthetics has a dialogical relationship to cultural institutions, it reflects the desire to establish collaborations with institutions that permit the development of shifts towards the relevant practices in a culture. In order to study that, proverbs have been taken from the Nadars of southern Tamil Nadu, especially in Kanniyakumari District. Nadars are identified into two major categories. As they are the residents of Virudhunagar, Madurai, Theni, and other cities in Tamil Nadu that are close to their home land, they are known as northern Nadars. The second category of southern Nadars are the inhabitants of Thoothukudi, Tirunelveli, and Kanniyakumari districts of southern Tamil Nadu. (Dennis) Thus, these three districts are considered the home land of the Nadars. The reconstructed history of the Nadars begins in the nineteenth century. Their original house land was Tiruchendur taluk of the modern Thoothukudi district of Tamil Nadu. (R) Their traditional occupation was toddy tapping. Most of the Nadars (or Shanars, as they were then known) were engaged in cultivation and climbing of the Palmyra. An endogamous sub-group called Nadan, “land of the soil,” owned the lands and the trees, and each Nadan had a group of dependent climbers to work for them. (Hardgrave, The Nadars of Tamil Nadu: The Political Culture of a Community in

Change.) So the idea of “kinship expression in proverbs” would like to be explored by analysing its social values from the perspective of social aesthetics.

Area of Study

Nadars of Tamil Nadu are diversified into several occupational groups ranging from mercantile activity to toddy tapping. Despite the variation in their occupation, they follow rigid rules in the areas of kinship, family, and marriage, and therefore it appears as though the Nadar community is highly traditional. It is an interesting phenomenon to study how this community negotiates between tradition and modernity to uphold their identity as a distinct group within the social groups of Tamil Nadu. In order to understand that this paper is an attempt to deal with kinship proverbs from a folkloric point of view.

Sources for the Material Discussed

The sources of the study were taken from the fieldwork done while documenting their life styles and personal narratives. As this paper analyses the kinship proverbs collected from Nadars of Tamil Nadu, the study area is confined to this community, which is the residence of Kanniyakumari, Tirunelveli, and Thoothukudi districts. Thus, analytically, oral narratives were considered primary sources. As they are the assets of a group which they expressed through their culture in all the time of life styles, proverbs have been taken for the discussion.

Meta-folklore of Nadars (Pertaining to their Lineage)

In general, proverbs ordinarily suggest a course of action or pass judgment on a

situation. Roger D. Abrahams states that “proverbs are short and witty traditional expressions that arise as part of everyday discourse as well as in the more highly structured situations of education and judicial proceedings.” It is wise, belongs to a society, and is applied by an individual to a particular situation. From the proverbs it is observed that the reality of kinship relation of Nadars by adopting different tools for analyzing with following titles.

Lineage is a term in kinship studies that gives meaning to a corporate descent group whose members can be traced by their genealogical links to a known common ancestor.

In other words, it can also be taken as the kinship relationship between an individual and the individual’s ancestors. In terms of lineage, Nadars identify themselves as a joint family system. The extension of a lineage is identified with the following proverbs:

Proverb 1

Ottan	Kandaal	Uravuatru	Pokum
Great-great-grandfather	if one sees	relationship	will come to an end

If one has a great-great-grandfather, then he may be the last of that generation, and he is about to initiate a new generation.

Proverb 2

Thaai	petru	Makal	petru	makaludaiya-makal	petru	uravu	Muriyum
Mother	gave birth	daughter	gave birth	daughter’s daughter	gave birth	relation	Will end up

When the granddaughter of a woman gives birth to a child, the woman will be unknown to her granddaughter’s daughter. Thus there is no available kinship term to call/address the relatives beyond this.

From the proverbs above said the length of lineage in a family is identified for four generations to the ego.

no words to call or term the kinship, at the same it is very rare the relative of ottan to be alive. The second proverb also highlights the lineage, which is meant as follows: as a mother gives birth to a daughter, then the daughter gives birth, and the daughter’s daughter also gives birth; now, a new lineage or next generation is started by cutting that entire existing element in the kinship.

Proverbial definitions of the role of Kinship The lifestyles of a community may be understood by receiving the resources of oral traditions, which constitute the whole knowledge system of a community; further, it reveals all its lifestyles through its ethnic genres. As kinship is a complex, dynamic and likely to change in practice, it is indeed important to study the particular element of unit of a community which makes larger changes at societal level. There are many

Figure 1 Family/Lineage

From the figure, it is observed that the first proverb symbolizes that if ego has “ottan,” then he is about to start a new generation through his lineage. Beyond ottan there is

collections of folklore such as folk songs (children’s songs, folk games, and marriage songs), folk tales, myths, proverbs, ballads, and customary practices, but less of these works have dealt with kinship and marriage. Moreover, no one has dealt with the kinship and marriage of Nadars. Nadars’ social network and records in folklore is an important area to be studied which remained unexplored in terms of folklore perspective.

Myths that deal with the origin of species, including humans, become intelligible when it is realized that they are the scheme of political and ceremonial relationships (Fortes). As Meyer Fortes noted about myth, myths especially origin myth of Nadars narrate about the kinship and marriage pattern and marriage alliance between two groups and denial of marriage as because of the person from outside the group. William R. Bascom emphasizes

the importance of the study of folklore in anthropology, especially in the fields of kinship, economics, law, and religion (Bascom). Richard Bauman quotes those words: “Folklore is a function of shared identity” (Bauman). Malinowski states that “human culture gives its members a definite vision of the world and a definite zest for life” (Malinowski, Argonauts of the Western Pacific). Robert Redfield defines worldview as “the way of people characteristically looking outward upon the universe” (Redfield). According to Clifford Geertz, “worldview” is nothing but the way a community thinks, what they actually are, and the concepts of nature, self, and society/community (Dundes).

From the proverbs it is observed that the reality of kinship relation in a family by adopting different tools for analysing with following titles.

I

aruvakkaaran	oravu	arutherinthaalum	pOvaathu	sokkaaran	oravu	southerinthaalum	pOvaathu
Agnate	Bond	Cut	Will not go	Agnates	Bond	Scoop	Will not go

One can never neglect his agnate’s relationship by cutting or scooping its roots. It is within it.

“One’s own sibling” or “immediate sibling” are used to describe agnates among the Nadars of Tamil Nadu, especially from Kanniyakumari district. This proverb emphasizes the harmony and bond between the siblings in the family. Although they are as close as siblings or distantly related, their bond cannot be concealed by any other activities. It will always bloom or grow new whenever they meet. Despite they had quarrel each other, they are brothers. That relationship has a special affinity for each other. No one can underestimate it. In order to expose the strong bond among the agnates, this proverb might have been created. From the above said discussion it is highlighted

that agnate relationship is fixed one they will never go away from the bond.

II

Sethaalum	sokkaran	kadakkaaran
Though dies	agnates	debtor

Despite an agnate’s death, he is indebted to his agnates

Agnates in the family have a very important role to play in the kin group of a family as well as in society. They need in all the vents of the family namely birth to funeral. On the one hand, in most of the villages, a family’s strength is measured by the number of agnates in the family. Even today, the strength of one’s ancestors is well appreciated by other families. Thus, the number of agnates will

be an indicator of the family's strength. A function at family will be more harmony when agnates' number is increased. So, that relation is decided by the birth in the same clan. Then it is recognized during the agnate's marriage. Finally, it gets rewarded by all the relatives. So, an agnate can never think to detach his membership from that clan. Knowingly or unknowingly, he is included as an agnate in the family by virtue of his birth in the same clan. That relation of agnate relation is not only used for getting rewarded by the fellow agnates, it is a ritual and also has the ritualistic status in a family to honor his agnate to his agnate in the funeral by providing/sharing his contribution of cloths or cash. It is understood as the token of respect as his agnate feels it even at last days in the earth. If anyone forgets or does not come to honor his agnate at his funeral, the family and society will not respect him. By having this practice at family and the society, he becomes an obligatory responsible person towards his agnate's family till he is alive. So, wherever he stays, but his representation should be made to equate his obligatory responsibility, either by his son when he is absent. By doing this ritual he is relieved from the obligatory responsibility from his elder/younger agnates. Though his agnate dies, his indebt is supposed to repay by doing his customary rights at his funeral ceremony.

Conclusion: Tradition is remembered through Kinship

As stated earlier about social aesthetics, to enhance the interpretation of kinship proverbs, the idea of social aesthetics is used in this paper. The usages of proverbs in day to day activities are found as classical tradition of the language as well as literature in a society. In that respect, John Lazarus points (Lazarus, 1894) out the usages of proverbs in which it explores the poetics and the heritage of the society. Despite

a proverb being told in the present, the responsibility goes to the ancestor of the addresser and addressee in the context. (Lourdu, 2007) From the proverbs dealt in earlier it is found as in the follows: Parallel cousins are known as pangali (sharer). As they are sharing their clan of each and every lineage, they are considered as pangali. Reflections from the genres about the pangali are found as in following: each and every pangali is bound to be committed to everyone. As they are sharing equal responsibility, the ritual also has a reflexive nature. So, a pangali's duty is to honor other pangali in all the life cycle ceremonies, which are considered obligatory. Another view on pangali of Nadar from the ethnic genres is that agnates (pangali) relationship is brought when a new lineage is born in family. It is brought by the blood, as this relationship of lineage is derived from the blood; it has the large extent till the known lineage. From the informant, it is found that there is an opinion about the agnate, which is to be careful with pangali. It is compared with the process of cutting palm fruit. One cannot easily cut the palm fruit as cutting other fruits. Palm fruit will have more fiber and flesh than the nuts. Each palm fruit has two or three nuts together. So, one can tear the fruit into two or three pieces according to the number of nuts in the fruit. The same technique has to be employed with pangali. Thus it is to be noted that pangali are interlinked each other. As they are connected with each one their characteristic dealing the matters will also be same. So, rather than the pangali, others should be very cautious about the pangali. Otherwise, the whole agnate will get together whenever the need arises to form an agnate. It is also to be noted that, though they are pangali, their dealings should be as clear as others. Despite the fact that all of them are considered ancestors, each and

every one has different needs and scope in every family.

It is extracted from the parallel cousin's role in a family that if anyone wants to have an alliance within the group, it is advised to maintain the relationship well. Thus, the above dealt proverbs stress on harmony with neighbor. The same is reiterated by telling through proverbs to recommend the community and family to follow/having relationship within. Thus it is considered a regulating authority in a family and in society as well. It is to be noted that the stagnating conceptualization among the folk communities is reflected in historical consciousness. (Vanamamalai, 1980; 2008 revised edition)

Bibliography

1. Abrahams, Roger D. "Proverbs and Proverbial Expressions." Dorson, Richard M. *Folklore and Folklife: An Introduction*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1972. 119.
2. Aristotle. *Poetics*. New Delhi: Finger Print Classics, 2018 (Reprint).
3. Bascom, William R. "Folklore and Anthropology." *The Journal of American Folklore*. Vol. 66. No. 262 (October–December, 1955): 262.
4. Bauman, Richard. "Differential Identity and the Social Base of Folklore." Abrahams, Richard Bauman and Roger D. And Other Neighborly Names: *Social Image and Cultural Process in Texas Folklore*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1972. 32.
5. Deitcher, David. 2002. 232.
6. Dennis, Templeman. *The Northern Nadars of Tamil Nadu: An Indian caste in the process of change*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996.
7. Dundes, Alan. *Interpreting Folklore*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1980.
8. Fortes, Meyer. *The Dynamics of Clanship Among the Tallensi: Being the First Part of an Analysis of the Social Structure of a Trans-Volta Tribe*. International African Institute, 1969.
9. Hardgrave, Robert L. 1969.
10. *The Nadars of Tamilnadu: The Political culture of a community in change*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1969.
11. Lazaras, John. *A Dictionary of Tamil Proverbs*, Madras. 1894.
12. Lourdu, S.D. "Tamil Proverbs: Structure, Semantics and Function." Chennai: United Writers, 2007. 188.
13. Malinowski. *Argonauts of the Western Pacific*. New York: Routledge, 1922, 2014 (Routledge).
14. *Argonauts of the Western Pacific*. New York: Routledge, 2014.
15. Redfield, Robert. *The primitive world and its transformations*. Cornell University Press, 1953.
16. Taylor, Archer. "The Wisdom of Many and the Wit of One." Mieder, Wolfgang and Alan Dundes. *The Wisdom of Many: Essays on the Proverb*. New York: Garland Publishing INC, 1981-reprinted. INC. p.3.
17. Vanamamalai, Naa. "Thiripuri Pazhamozhikalum Inaiyaana Tamil Pazhamozhikal." Naa., Vanamamalai. *Pazhankathaikalum Pazhamozhikalum: Samooka, Maanidaviyal Aaivuk Katturaikal*. Chennai: New Century Book House (P) Ltd., 1980 (2008 revised edition). 123.